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SELF-DEFENSE AS AN EDUCATIONAL ACTION FOR INCLUSION

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ABSTRACT

Self advocacy refers to the ability of people with intellectual or multiple disabilities to express themselves, make their own decisions and defend their rights. It consists of a program that originated in the APAE Network in defense of valuing diversity and promoting the dignity of children, young adults and the elderly with intellectual and multiple disabilities. In this way, this study seeks to analyze self-defense as an educational action for inclusion. This research consists of a case study of an observational and documentary nature with a qualitative approach, in which the actions of self-defense carried out at APAE Niterói over the years with those assisted were observed. Documents were analyzed, including records of meetings of self-defenders and the researchers' field diary. Over the years, there has been a growth in the discussions and actions of the self-defense with great support from people with disabilities. However, it can be seen that the self-defenders' demands have remained almost the same over the years, as is the case with bullying in schools and discrimination. We conclude that although legislation seeks to reduce these gaps, very little concrete action has been taken by society to remedy them.